

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

To Cite:

Bamigboye, S. O. Growth Performance and Photochemical Composition of Broiler Chickens Fed Diets Containing Pawpaw Seed (Carica Papaya) Oil. *IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal* 2024; Vol 3, Issue 1, pp. 126-132. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12736932>

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Peer-Review History

Received: 22nd May, 2024

Reviewed & Revised: 23/May / 2024 to 12th July/2024

Accepted: 13th July 2024

Published: July 2024

Peer-Review Model

External peer-review was done through double-blind method.

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

ISSN: xxxx-xxxx

URL: <https://sites.google.com/view/sherwanjournals/integratemind-journal>

Ethics

No animal studies are presented in this manuscript.

No human studies are presented in this manuscript.

No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in this study.

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Growth Performance and Photochemical Composition of Broiler Chickens Fed Diets Containing Pawpaw Seed (Carica Papaya) Oil

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12736932>

ABSTRACT

This study is aimed to evaluate the effect of broiler chickens fed diets containing pawpaw (Carica papaya) seed oil (PSO) as a feed additive on growth performance and phytochemical of broiler chicken. Five experimental diets each were formulated during the starter (1-28days) and finisher (29-56days) phases such that the basal diets were supplemented with 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 and 0.4 % respectively. Pawpaw seed oil. A total of 195 day-old Arbor Acre chicks were randomly allocated to the five dietary treatments comprising of three replicates each in a completely randomized design. Phytochemical analysis of CSO showed that it contained flavonoids, Phytate, Oxalate, Saponins, and Tannins at 9.07%, 1.30%, 0.02%, 2.88%, 4.77% respectively. Weight gain revealed that birds in treatment 3, 4 and 5 had the highest weight gain of 1899.9 g, 1960.8 g and 2300.2 g followed by treatment 2 (1790.5 g) and treatment 1 (1755.2 g) ($p < 0.05$). Total feed intake and mortality were not influenced by the treatment ($p > 0.05$). It was concluded that dietary supplementation of PSO up to 0.4 ml in the diet of broilers without causing any deleterious effect on their growth performance.

Keywords: Carica papaya oil, Phytochemical, Broilers, Diet.

1. INTRODUCTION

Papaya (Carica papaya) seed is one of the agro-industrial by-products that have been included in poultry rations, due to its substantial amounts of crude protein, fat, and ash (Adesuyi et al., 2011). Papaya seed also contains some functional properties that may act as growth promoters (Muazu et al., 2020; Musa et al., 2021), anti-microbial and anti-parasitic factors (Kumar et al., 2017; Adewale et al., 2021) and Masfufatun et al., 2019; Alagbe, 2022), and immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory agents (Kadiri et al., 2016; Alagbe et al. 2023 and Pandey et al., 2016) for poultry. Taking these facts into consideration, papaya seed may be used as feed ingredient to reduce feed cost as well as functional feedstuff to improve the health and well-being of poultry. Papaya is a tropical fruit that is available throughout the year (Ameen et al., 2012). Papaya fruit is commonly consumed fresh as a dessert or juice. Papaya seeds are black in color and embedded in the fruit pulp (Kadiri et al., 2016). In general, the seed from ripe papaya represents of about 16% of the fresh fruit weight and is considered as a by-product. The abundant availability throughout the year and less economic value of papaya seed has encouraged the nutritionists to exploit such by-product as a protein-rich feed ingredient as well as functional feedstuff for poultry. The updates regarding the nutritional contents of papaya seed, the potential of papaya seed as an alternative to conventional protein-rich ingredient, the growth promoting effect of feeding papaya seed, the antimicrobial and anti-parasitic activities of papaya seed, anti-oxidative activities of papaya seed, and the immunomodulatory activity of papaya seed on poultry are presented in the present review. Therefore, incorporating pawpaw seed oil into the diet of broiler is still a novel concept that is yet to be fully explore. The objective of the present study was to evaluate the growth performance and to evaluate the photochemical composition of pawpaw seed oil.

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2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted at the Department of Animal Science, Faculty of Agriculture, university of Abuja teaching and research farm, main campus, along Airport road, Gwagwalada, Abuja. Gwagwalada is one of the six (6) area councils of the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria. It lies between latitude 08°51 and 09°37N and longitude of 007°20 and 007°51 E and the land mass covers 65sq km.

2.1. Papaya Seed Oil Extraction

The papaya seed was procured from the local market within Gwagwalada market, Abuja (Nigeria). Pawpaw seed oil was extracted using the steam distillation technique. The steam distillation procedure requires a digital weighing scale, a round bottom flask, and distilled water. 50 grams of ground pawpaw seed was weighed into a round bottom flask and mixed with 250 ml of distilled water. The condenser was set up above the flask with a circular bottom after the mixture was transferred to a glass yarn heating mantle and heated to a temperature of 80°C. The mixture is boiled vigorously for a period of 15 minutes, after which the distillate is gathered in a beaker until no more oil drips are visible. It is then poured into a separatory funnel to yield pawpaw seed essential oil.

2.2. Design and Managements of Experimental Birds

One hundred and Ninety-five (195) day old white marshal broiler starter chicks was purchased from a reputable hatchery. The chicks on arrival at the experiment site were housed in battery cage with twine mesh at the base for easy collection of faeces. The cage was disinfected and cleared a week before the birds arrived. At arrival, the birds were given anti-stress with antibiotics for the first week and were allowed them to adapt to the environment. Feeders and drinkers were provided. The performance of the chicks was monitor and the initial weights of the chick were recorded at the commencement of the experiment. Weekly body weight gained and weekly feed intake record was taken. The birds was weighed and randomly allotted into five (5) treatments with three (3) replicates per treatments in a completely randomized design. Each replicate contained thirteen (13) birds making 39birds per treatment. Heat and light was provided throughout the experimental period using kerosene lantern, electricity. Feed and water was provided ad-libitum and the experiment will last for a period of 56days. Routine vaccination and other medications was administered at when due.

2.3. Experimental Design and Diet

Diets 1was formulated to meet the nutrient requirement for broilers according to Aduku, 1994 as presented in Table 1. Experimental diet at the starter phase (1-28th days) and finisher phase (29-56th days) was contained 23.30% crude protein and 21.40% crude protein respectively. The experimental set up is shown below:

Diet 1: Basal diet without synthetic antibiotics and pawpaw seed oil

Diet 2: Basal diet + 0.1ml

Diet 3: Basal diet + 0.2ml

Diet 4: Basal diet + 0.3ml

Diet 5: Basal diet +0.4ml

3. DATA COLLECTION

3.1. Growth Performance

The initial body weight of the chicks was recorded on arrival day and weekly basis to assess their weight gain. Feed intake was monitored by taking notes of the difference between feed served and the feed left over after 24 hours. The feed conversion ratio was also calculated by dividing the feed intake by the weight gain. Percentage of mortality was also determined by the number of dead birds divided by the total number of birds multiply by 100.

- ❖ Feed intake(g) = $\text{Feed supplied(g)} - \text{Left over(g)}$
- ❖ Weight gain (g) = $\text{Final weight (g)} - \text{initial weight(g)}$
- ❖ Average daily feed (ADG) = $\frac{\text{Final body weight} - \text{initial body weight}}{\text{Total days of the experiment}}$
- ❖ Average daily feed intake (ADI) = $\frac{\text{Total feed intake}}{\text{Total days of the experiment}}$
- ❖ Dressing Percentage = $\frac{\text{Dressed weight}}{\text{Live weight}} \times 100$
- ❖ Feed conversion ration (CR) = $\frac{\text{Feed intake(g)}}{\text{Weight gain}}$
- ❖ Mortality = $\frac{\text{Number of dead/replicate}}{\text{Total no o birds in replicate.}} \times 100$

4. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All data collected was subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS (25.0) and significant means will be separated using Duncan multiple range tests significant will be declared if $P \leq 0.05$ (see, Table 1).

Table 1: Ingredient Composition of the Experimental Diets

Ingredients	Starter	Finisher
Maize	52.00	60.00
Wheat offal	2.50	5.00
Soya bean meal	30.00	25.00
Groundnut cake	8.00	4.00
Fish meal	2.00	2.00
Limestone	1.50	1.50
Bone meal	3.00	3.00
Lysine	0.20	0.20
Methionine	0.20	0.20
Premix	0.25	0.25
Salt	0.30	0.30
Toxin binder	0.10	0.10
Total	100	100
Determined analysis (% DM)		
Crude protein	23.30	21.40
Crude fibre	4.18	5.01
Ether extract	4.03	4.47
Calcium	1.50	1.60
Phosphorus	0.58	0.66
Energy (Kcal/kg)	2900.3	3200.8

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from this experiment “growth performance and photochemical composition of broiler chickens fed diets containing pawpaw seed (*carica papaya*) oil is discussed below. Table 2 Shows the results of effect of graded levels of garlic oil on the performance of the experimental birds in (1-8th weeks) phase. Average daily weight gain, feed intake and feed conversion ratio. Body weight gain in treatment 2, 3, 4 and 5 were higher ($P < 0.05$) than birds in treatment 1. Average daily feed intake in treatment 1 and 2 were similar ($P > 0.05$) while mortality was higher in group 1 relative to other treatments ($P < 0.05$). Overall production (1 - 56days), average daily weight gain, feed intake and mortality were significantly influenced by the treatments ($P < 0.05$). Lowest weight gain was recorded among birds in group 1 relative to the other treatment. Conversely, feed intake among birds in group 4 and 5 were higher as presented in the earlier section, papaya seed contains a substantial amount of protein and may thereby be used as an alternative protein feed ingredient in poultry rations. With crude protein of 24-30% (Muazu *et al.*, 2020, Kumar *et al.*, 2017, Santos *et al.*, 2014, Seshamamba *et al.*, 2018), papaya seed meal may be exploited as the alternative protein feed ingredient for poultry. In the context of protein digestibility, (El-Safyet *et al.*, 2012) reported that in vitro protein digestibility of papaya seed meal was 80.7%. ($P < 0.05$) than those in other treatments. Higher mortality rate was recorded in group 1 (1.34 %) while none was recorded in the other treatments fed diets supplemented with PSO. Higher feed conversion ratio was recorded in treatment 2, 3, 4 and 5 relative to birds in treatment 1 ($P < 0.05$). The medicinal value of plants lies in some chemical substances that produce a definite physiological action on the animal’s body and these chemical substances are called phytochemicals (Singh *et al.*, 2021; Adewale *et al.*, 2021. These are non- nutritive chemicals that have disease preventive properties and translate to better feed conversion among birds (Shittu *et al.*, 2021). The results obtained in this experiment suggests that PSO effectively enhanced digestion and absorption of nutrients, host metabolism and maintaining a healthy gut to mount against diseases among birds in group 2, 3, 4 and 5. No mortality was recorded among birds in fed PSO which indicates that it is capable of preventing dysbacteriosis or dysbiosis in the gut, thus lowering the amount of pathogenic bacteria and increase the quantity of beneficial bacteria (symbionts) (Olafadehan *et al.*, 2020; Oloruntola *et al.*, 2018). The presence of benzylisothiocyanate in PSO suggests that it has antimicrobial and antibacterial properties, thus lowering the intestinal pH against pathogenic organisms (Singh *et al.*, 2021). The outcome of this result is in consonance with the reports of (Olafadehan *et al.*, 2020).

Table 2: The Effect of Graded Levels of Pawpaw Seed Oil on the Performance of Broiler Chickens (1-56days)

Parameters%	T1	T2	T3	T5	T5	SEM
IBW (g/bird)	45.04	45.00	45.03	45.01	45.01	-
FBW (g/bird)	1700.2 ^c	1804.5 ^b	1944.8 ^a	2005.8 ^a	2454.73 ^a	8.75
WG (g/bird)	1755.2 ^c	1790.5 ^b	1899.8 ^a	1960.8 ^a	2300.23 ^a	8.06
TFI (g/bird)	3703.1	3701.9	3900.8	3910.2	4200.3	9.03
FCR	2.45 ^c	2.26 ^b	2.10 ^b	2.14 ^a	2.37 ^b	0.02
Mortality (%)	1.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01

^{a,b,c} means with same superscript are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

T1: Basal diet (without pawpaw seed oil); T2: Basal diet + 0.1 ml PSO/kg; T3:0.2ml PSO/kg;

T4: 0.3 ml Pawpaw seed oil/kg;T5:0.4 ml Pawpaw seed oil/ kg; SEM = standard error of mean

Table 3 shows the effect of photochemical composition of broiler chickens fed diets containing pawpaw seed. Phytochemicals can be simply be defined as plant's chemicals. They are a large group of plant-derived compounds hypothesized to be responsible for much of the disease protection conferred by diets high in vegetables, fruits, beans, cereals and plant-based beverages such as tea and wine (Abugba and Shelaby 2018; Plamada and Vodnar 2022). Phytochemicals have several properties and therapeutic uses. For example, flavonoids have anti-allergic, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. Tannins have wound-healing properties (Anjum et al., 2013; Martel et al., 2020). Some phytochemicals are anti-nutritional factors. Anti-nutritional factors are substances generated in natural food and/or feedstuffs by the normal metabolism of species and several mechanisms. They interfere with the absorption of nutrients and digestive processes (Salehi et al., 2018). Although phytochemicals have beneficial effects, it is worth noting that excessive consumption can have detrimental effects on humans and animals. (Aravind et al., 2021). This table reveals the phytochemical constituents in papaya oil. The sample contained flavonoids, Phytate, Oxalate, Saponins, and Tannins at 9.07%, 1.30%, 0.02%, 2.88%, 4.77% respectively.

Table 3: Phytochemical Composition of Pawpaw Seed Oil (Pso)

Parameters	% composition
Tannins	4.77
Saponins	2.88
Oxalate	0.02
Phytate	1.30
Flavonoids	9.07

The presence of tannin corroborated the result of Dwivedi et al., (2020), who was reported the presence of pawpaw seed oil extracts. The presence of saponins in the pawpaw seed oil samples also corroborated the results of Ukpo et al., (2017), Salehi et al., (2018) and Singh (2020), who showed that saponin is still present even after processing the seed to oil protein concentrates. It has been reported that saponins have anti-diarrheal and anthelmintic properties. (Singh et al., 2020). Phytate is an anti-nutrient compound known to complex with protein and mineral, hence interfering with their diet absorption. There are several methods of decreasing the inhibitory effect of phytate mineral absorption: cooking, fermentation, soaking and autolysis (Plamada and Vodnar 2022). It has been reported that flavonoids have anti-inflammatory effect (Choy et al., 2019). Flavonoids were found to be present in all samples of PSO from all three locations, and this corroborated the results of Ukpo et al., (2017) and Singh et al., (2020), who found flavonoids to be present in the oil of *C. papaya*. The presence of these phyto-constituents in PSO shows that it possesses medicinal properties viz: antimicrobial, antioxidant, antifungal, antibacterial, hepato-protective, immuno-stimulatory amongst others (Alagbe et al., 2023). However, the concentration of these compounds are lower than values reported by Daniel et al (2023). These variation could be attributed to specie, age of plant, geographical location and processing methods (Musa et al, 2021; Adewale et al, 2021).

6. CONCLUSIONS

Five experiments were conducted to determine the best level of pawpaw seed oil addition in broiler diets with 0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.3% inclusion level. 0.3ml pawpaw seed oil addition level compared favourably with highest growth rate and Caricca papaya essential oil is nutritionally non-toxic and safe without affecting their performance and health condition. The best graded level of pawpaw seed oil inclusion that gave optimum performance was at 0.3ml inclusion rate.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

Funding

The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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